

Supply chain performance scandals of e-commerce industry: qualitative evidence from Bangladesh

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study is to present the supply chain performance scandals of E-commerce industry in Bangladesh. Based on this objective, this study followed a newspaper-based content analysis methodology. A structured systematic way was followed here. This study finds that both the e-commerce company has numerous scandals related to their services. However, Evaly is completely running their business very technically with some MLM business characteristics. That raises the questions about their supply chain systems. This study will have significant contribution to e-commerce industry research in Bangladesh.

Keywords: SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT; E-COMMERCE INDUSTRY; BANGLADESH; CRITICISM OF E-COMMERCE INDUSTRY IN BANGLADESH; E-COMMERCE SCANDALS; E-COMMERCE PROBLEMS

Introduction

If quality products can be purchased at home, why should people go to the market with any more difficulty? People are taking on a lot of such things as they keep pace with the world over time. It is only natural that people will be inclined to the online market if they get the benefits of goods that are running at home with just a few clicks. This Covid-19 period taught the people of the country that potatoes can also be buy online. Especially the people of the capital. There was already a tendency to buy electronics products, clothing, household appliances. Even now many people are

selling raw markets online, medicine is also one of these online based products. All in all, e-commerce entrepreneurs are seeing good times in the coming days. According to them, a part of the habits of online buy and transaction will remain in the future. However, a large section of buyers did not have the experience of shopping online. They bought products online during the season. This has led to habituating. It is expected that a part of them will remain online buyers in the future. Not everyone has a debit or credit card, however, many have open accounts of Mobile financial service (MFS). Nowadays almost 40 per cent of our transactions

are through MFS. It was 20 per cent before the Covid-19.

The e-commerce sector in Bangladesh started to gain momentum from 2013. Two incidents took place that year. First, Bangladesh Bank lifted the ban on international purchases with credit cards. In the same year, mobile operators in the country launched the fastest third generation Internet Service (3G). This was followed by the launch of the fourth generation Internet Service (4G). People's tendency to use smartphones has increased. On the other hand, new investments have come in the e-commerce sector. All in all, the sector has been expanded as well as the number of online buyers has increased ¹.

Many people have bought various products from online marketplace during the Covid-19 season. Many of those buying goods from online are cheating. The level of cheating with substandard products is increasing day by day. This is why even many online sites have been the most accused in the Directorate of National Consumer Rights Protection. There is now a mountain of complaints against both Daraz and Evaly in the consumer department. They been spared legal loopholes even if the buyer has been cheated since its establishment. And sometimes the company is getting away with very small number of fines. Even most cases, buyers are losing full amount that they paid for the products. In most cases, seller send substandard product, useless products. Even in some cases, there is no product in the box. For these reasons this case study highlights the cheating cases that was happened to the buyers. Based on this concept the findings of this case study are designed in the following section ²

Materials and methods

This study follows qualitative research method to find the objective of this study. All the data of this study has been collected from the secondary data sources ³. Mainly data was collected from newspaper, reviews, and direct interviews of some buyers. First of all, the raw data was collected to analyze the criticism of the e-commerce industry. After that the criticisms are separated based on the buyer's opinion. Sometimes some buyers put some opinion those seemed fake to us. That's why this study didn't consider those opinions. This study has collected the opinion of the responsible authority such as consumer rights lawyers, e-cab members, responsible persons from national consumer rights authority, and so on. Whatever, the findings of this study

¹ Farhana Zaman and Priyabrata Chowdhury, "Technology Driven Banking in Bangladesh: Present Status, Future Prospects and Challenges," *BUP Journal* 1, no. 1 (2012): 56–78; Nofie Iman, "Is Mobile Payment Still Relevant in the Fintech Era?," *Electronic Commerce Research and Applications* 30, no. May (2018): 72–82, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eelerap.2018.05.009>; Md. Mohiuddin, "Overview the E-Commerce in Bangladesh," *IOSR Journal of Business and Management* 16, no. 7 (2014): 01–06, <https://doi.org/10.9790/487x-16720106>; Bhowmik, "The Present E-Commerce Situation in Bangladesh for B2C E-Commerce"; Saif Hossain, "Internship Report on E-Commerce Business Opportunities and Challenges in Bangladesh Submitted to Prepared By," n.d.; Bhowmik, "The Present E-Commerce Situation in Bangladesh for B2C E-Commerce."

² By Ahmed, Saad Ishtiaque, and Adib Sarwar, "E-Commerce in Bangladesh," no. January (2016); Mohiuddin, "Overview the E-Commerce in Bangladesh"; Bhowmik, "The Present E-Commerce Situation in Bangladesh for B2C E-Commerce."

³ Md. Morshadul Hasan, Lu Yajuan, and Shajib Khan, "Promoting China's Inclusive Finance Through Digital Financial Services," *Global Business Review*, 2020, 097215091989534, <https://doi.org/10.1177/0972150919895348>; Md. Morshadul Hasan, Lu Yajuan, and Appel Mahmud, "Regional Development of China's Inclusive Finance Through Financial Technology," *SAGE Open* 10, no. 1 (2020): 215824401990125, <https://doi.org/10.1177/2158244019901252>; Md. Morshadul Hasan and Appel Mahmud, "Risks Management of Ready-Made Garments Industry in Bangladesh," *International Research Journal of Business Studies* 10, no. 1 (2017): 1–13, <https://doi.org/doi.org/10.21632/irjbs.10.1.1-13>.

are presented in the following sections.

Results

E-commerce industry in Bangladesh

It has to be said that Bangladesh has come a long way in building a digital Bangladesh ⁴. As a result of strong measures taken by the government, significant developments can be seen in the last few years in various sectors including digital or information technology-based administration system, business and trade, agriculture, healthcare, education, public service ⁵. At present, the whole country has entered under 4-G network. According to media reports, Bangladesh will launch 5-G by 2020. Already, a total of 5,275 unions across the country have been covered by the Internet network, which is a life-saver for a large marginalized population, such as assisting in providing various government services including examination results, college-university admission information, employment information, utility bill payment, e-mail communication, birth-death registration, mobile banking ⁶.

E-commerce is the means of purchasing and selling all kinds of physical and digital products and services through the internet network, using electronic devices such as personal computers, laptops, tablets, mobile phones, etc. through web and electronic data exchange ⁷. It is basically a modern digital medium for online business, which facilitates coordination between different sectors of government, facilitates business transactions and communication, and creates employment opportunities across the country ⁸. The growing globalization process has led to the spread of e-commerce and popularity worldwide.

The most positive aspects of the e-commerce sector are: create opportunities to engage with the international price process; Creating free access to large markets and research; Develop and enhance the efficiency of the

⁴ Mohammad Nurunnabi and Monirul Alam Hossain, "The Voluntary Disclosure of Internet Financial Reporting (IFR) in an Emerging Economy: A Case of Digital Bangladesh," *Journal of Asia Business Studies* 6, no. 1 (2012): 17–42, <https://doi.org/10.1108/15587891211190688>; Christopher S. Walsh, "Going Digital on Low-Cost Mobile Phones in Bangladesh," 2011, https://doi.org/10.5176/2251-1814_eel54.

⁵ Xiaolin Lin, Xuequn Wang, and Nick Hajli, "Building E-Commerce Satisfaction and Boosting Sales: The Role of Social Commerce Trust and Its Antecedents," *International Journal of Electronic Commerce* 23, no. 3 (2019): 328–63, <https://doi.org/10.1080/10864415.2019.1619907>; Rajneesh Shahjee, "The Impact Of Electronic Commerce On Business Organization," *An International Peer Reviewed & Referred: Scholarly Research Journal for Interdisciplinary Studies* 4, no. 27 (2016): 3130–40; Md. Morshadul Hasan and Appel Mahmud, "Deadly Incidents in Bangladeshi Apparel Industry and Illustrating the Causes and Effects of These Incidents," *Journal of Finance and Accounting* 5, no. 5 (2017): 193, <https://doi.org/10.11648/j.jfa.20170505.13>; Md. Morshadul Hasan et al., "Trends and Impacts of Different Barriers on Bangladeshi RMG Industry's Sustainable Development," *International Research Journal of Business Studies* 11, no. 3 (2018): 245–60, <https://doi.org/10.21632/irjbs.11.3.245-260>.

⁶ Nitai Chandra, Nitai Chandra Debnath, and Abdullah Al Mahmud, "The Environment of E-Commerce in Bangladesh," *Daffodil International University Journal of Business and Economics* 2, no. 2 (2007), <http://hdl.handle.net/20.500.11948/640>; Roni Bhowmik and International Business, "The Present E-Commerce Situation in Bangladesh for B2C E-Commerce," *International Journal of Economics and Research* 03, no. 05 (2012): 77–91; Farjana Akhtar, "Farjana Akhtar GROWTH AND CHALLENGES OF E-COMMERCE A Comparison between Bangladesh and Finland Master 's Thesis," no. September (2019); Appel Mahmud et al., "Corporate Social Responsibility Programs and Community Perceptions of Societal Progress in Bangladesh: A Multimethod Approach," *SAGE Open* 10, no. 2 (2020), <https://doi.org/10.1177/2158244020924046>.

⁷ Karim and Qi, "E-Commerce Development in Bangladesh"; Bhowmik, "The Present E-Commerce Situation in Bangladesh for B2C E-Commerce"; Mohiuddin, "Overview the E-Commerce in Bangladesh."

⁸ Bhowmik, "The Present E-Commerce Situation in Bangladesh for B2C E-Commerce"; Bhowmik; Bhowmik and Business, "The Present E-Commerce Situation in Bangladesh for B2C E-Commerce"; Bhowmik, "The Present E-Commerce Situation in Bangladesh for B2C E-Commerce."

internal market; Easy and short transaction expenses; Create new export markets and increase export income; New industrialization based on demand including SMEs; Creating new business entrepreneurs based on field; Create more new employment, and so on ⁹.

There are several challenges on the e-commerce industry in Bangladesh. Such as crisis of delivery of goods is one of these. If one orders a laptop worth 50,000 BDT online, then various thoughts will come to mind in case of paying that money in advance. In addition, many fall due to lack of funding. Some people do not keep the quality of the product. As a result, shoppers can't trust online shopping. Many people cheat the buyer by trying to make quick profit without patience. Product quality verification is not selected. Besides, there is no policy in this sector yet. Whatever, those who want to become e-commerce entrepreneurs in Bangladesh have many challenges. Many people think that e-commerce is just an online shopping site. E-commerce is actually much more. Of course, you need to have technical knowledge to create an online shopping site. But with that comes a few more types of knowledge and skills. Besides, there is no investment in this sector. It is difficult to get a loan ¹⁰. Therefore, the entrepreneurs of this sector are demanding at least 51 percent domestic investment in e-commerce companies¹¹. Whatever, some specific challenges of the e-commerce sector in Bangladesh have given below: e-commerce subsidiary suitable national policy, specific roadmap for e-commerce development, financial transactions security, slow and expensive internet, delivery channel, inter-operable infrastructure, skilled e-commerce technology assistant administration, judiciary and human resources are lacking, lack of a confident e-commerce environment, lack of public access to online shopping and fear, lack of specific mechanisms to eliminate consumer dissatisfaction, the e-commerce sector is not allowed to provide banking facilities, no incentive package for the development of the e-commerce sector, lack of adequate publicity etc.

Bangladesh's e-commerce sector grew by 72 percent in 2016, a promising growth in the history of e-commerce in Bangladesh. According to Bangladesh Bank statistics, total transactions through e-commerce were 3.59 billion Tk. (US\$50 million) in January-September 2016, up from a record 2.16 billion (US\$30 million) in 2015. The number of credit card users is higher than debit cards in the country and the number of Internet users is more than 60 million, which is about one-third of the country's total population. This new business system can only be associated with the basic knowledge of ICT and e-commerce without the help of any middle-class. In this regard, the Government's Vision-2021: Digital Bangladesh implementation process will be more rapid and various activities including establishment of exportable multi-faceted industries, multi-

⁹ Karim and Qi, "E-Commerce Development in Bangladesh"; Ahmed, Ishtiaque, and Sarwar, "E-Commerce in Bangladesh"; Mohiuddin, "Overview the E-Commerce in Bangladesh"; Bhowmik, "The Present E-Commerce Situation in Bangladesh for B2C E-Commerce."

¹⁰ Karim and Qi, "E-Commerce Development in Bangladesh"; Abdul Gaffar Khan, "Electronic Commerce: A Study on Benefits and Challenges in an Emerging Economy," *Type: Double Blind Peer Reviewed International Research Journal Publisher: Global Journals Inc* 16, no. 1 (2016); Akhtar, "Farjana Akhtar GROWTH AND CHALLENGES OF E-COMMERCE A Comparison between Bangladesh and Finland Master ' s Thesis"; Minhaj Ferdous and Abu Ishtiaque, "Prospects of E-Commerce in Pharmaceutical Industry of Bangladesh: Lessons from the Case of Drugstore. Com," *Journal of Business Studies* 34, no. 3 (2013).

¹¹ <https://www.techjano.com/ই-কমার্স-খাতের-বর্তমানে-ক/>

faceted product diversification and market expansion, product rights determination will be carried out.

Daraz BD

Daraz is a Chinese-owned online marketplace that operates in South Asia. It was established in 2012 under the ownership of German company Rocket Internet. In 2015, Daraz started operations in Bangladesh called 'Daraz Bangladesh'. After the start of the proceedings, Mushfiqur Rahim, the captain of the Bangladesh national cricket team, became the goodwill ambassador. In 2015, they launched mobile apps for android and iPhone users for customers. In early 2017, Kaymu, an e-commerce company that operated in Bangladesh, merged with Daraz. It was established in Pakistan in 2012. It started operations in Bangladesh and Myanmar in 2015. In September 2015, the company gained 50 million euros in investment from the UK's state-owned Development Finance Institute. Daraz acquired Kaymu, another e-commerce industry in Bangladesh, in July 2016. However, finally Daraz was bought by Alibaba group in May 2018. On May 9, 2018, the International Daraz Group was bought by The Alibaba Group, a Chinese multinational company and e-commerce giant. Daraz, which is controlled by Alibaba group, currently provides e-commerce services called Daraz, Shop and Lazada in various Asian countries including Pakistan, Sri Lanka, Nepal, Myanmar, Thailand, Singapore, Philippines, Vietnam, Hong Kong besides Bangladesh.

Criticism of Daraz

Daraz is the most popular e-commerce site in Bangladesh. Thousands of customers buy products from Daraz nowadays. However, there are numerous scandals of Daraz, these are mention in the following section.

- The company is cheating in various ways, including ordering a product and ordering other goods, sending substandard and adulterated goods to the consumer's address. This is how Farhan Tanvir, who lives in Darus Salam in the capital, recently bought substandard goods from Daraz. He bought 7 liters of Mobil in a few rounds from Daraz for his motorcycle. After using it, he found out that the mobiles were completely adulterated. His motorcycle engine was burnt using this mobile. After showing the motorcycle to one renowned motorbike service shop, he came to know that his motorcycle was damaged due to the use of adulterated Mobil. He approached the *Directorate of National Consumer Rights Protection* seeking remedies. He lodged a written complaint with the department on November 23, 2020. Complaint No.37238. So far, four rounds of hearings have been held in the consumer department, but he has not yet received any remedies.
- Earlier, another complaint was lodged with the consumer department by a buyer named Mahmood. He made payments to buy headphones, but he was sent from Daraz to the OTG cable. Another buyer bought a Samsung mobile from Daraz, sending cloth raw soap to his address. The incident was long ago and there was a lot of uproar about it at that time.

- Mahfuzur Rahman, bought the power bank from Daraz. After receiving the product, he found that the power bank was completely damaged. Daraz complained but he did not get any remedies. In this way, Daraz is cheating the buyer with a new strategy. Their deception doesn't stop in any way.
- Another buyer, same silent, ordered a selfie stick and found the discarded portion of the abandoned scotch top. This is how shoppers are being duped one after the other through online shop Daraz. Without naming him, a YouTuber said that not only Daraz, but all the e-sites have the same problem. They just look at the profit of the business, not the interests of the customer. Our aim is to prevent people from falling into the trap of the offers offered by those sites. YouTubers tell you this out of responsibility that others should not fall into the trap even if they are cheated themselves. In this regard, Daraz's lawyer barrister Ziaur Rahman added, "In fact, the people of the country are yet to fully get over the business of goods through online platforms. For many, the issue is new. That is why daraz has taken initiatives to sensitize the buyer. Daraz authorities have formed a separate team to look into the problems of buyers who have bought and cheated goods. They are regularly talking to buyers, making them aware. In addition, training is being provided to make the buyer more aware of the purchase of the product. I think the allegations against Daraz are declining much more than before because of these initiatives.
- One customer Rahmatullah told Daraz.com sold fake Xiaomi power bank's multiple times to me. The hypocrisy of the famous Daraz.com Bangladesh (see www.daraz.com.bd). On August 24 I ordered two Xiaomi mi v2 10000mAh power banks, the delivery date was September 2, 2020. But after getting the product in hand, I'm disappointed, checking here the code that <https://www.mi.com/en/verify/> to check if it's original. After a while, take a look at the packet and see <http://chaxunmi.cn/>!! I'm surprised, a little google-like it's a fake website that looks mi.com/verify. I saw a post on Xiaomi's official forum with a link <http://en.miui.com/thread-1113758-1>-I didn't have to understand. On September 4, I ordered another order for me, realizing that he had caught fake products. This time on September 12, I got a fake Chaksunmi power bank in my hand, as soon as I returned it, but sent it with a clear so that I could not return it immediately. Then the days go by, I call again and again, mail the product and don't take the return. Today, if you call from another number, show the reverse cup, mail and show the information from the email you bought. However, I have mailed with evidence twice that will not work either. On the other hand, the order statement has disappeared from my account. I shared the video to save ordinary buyers from cheating, so forced to provide returns through the Daraz app. I didn't even request you to share it.
- Daraz's 1 tk offer trap targets cheating of lakhs of takas! Online shopping 'Daraz' is openly running fancy canons at the nose of the authorities concerned to prevent cyber monitoring and fraud. A car worth Tk 16 lakh for just Tk. 1! 'Daraz' is targeting to take crores of takas from many customers to

trap such innovative frauds. The fraud organization has launched a gambling company called 'Quiz' and 'Campaign' to disguise cheating. Such unethical activities are not known to the authorities concerned! The clever duped 'Daraz' is attracting customers by turning the gambling spin on the monitor screen online.

- Daraz.com was capitalizing on Coronavirus and selling a 50 Tk (0.5 USD) mask for 2,255 Tk (nearly 26USD) at the very beginning of Covid-19 period. A mobile court of rapid action battalion (RAB) fined Daraz Tk 2 lakh for selling masks at an additional price. The fine was imposed in a raid led by RAB headquarters executive magistrate Sarwar Alam in Banani in the capital from noon to night on March 15 this year. According to RAB's mobile court sources, the court officials visited Daraz's headquarters in Banani at the beginning of the raid. From there, raids were also conducted at the Tejgaon office. At this time, there is clearly evidence of Daraz's lack of surveillance in the sale of masks. Due to lack of proper surveillance, a Chittagong firm was selling masks at high prices in Daraz.
- Mehdi Hasan, a customer from Wari area, was cheated by buying goods from Daraz. He bought a lungi from Daraz. His order number is 609077586877100. He questioned the quality of that lungi. He said, 'The lungi I ordered was priced at Tk 450. 287 is taken from the discount. But after opening the packet, I see that it is unusable. They (Daraz) bring goods from the dealers. Daraz does not keep any check on whether the dealer gave good or bad goods. Daraz says they make quality mains, but they're not really on edge.'
- Babul is a customer of Dhanmondi area. He bought two pants and a polo shirt from Daraz. His order number is 60888067420921. He buys 3 products from the said order ID. The customer said the quality of the 3 products is questionable. A polo shirt is priced at Tk 1000. 220 is taken from the customer by discounting that product. The original of one pant is Tk. 1350, discount is Tk. 240 and another pant is Tk 799, discount is Tk. 228. Tk. 60 to 180 was taken to deliver each product. He told "*I saw Daraz's advertise on Facebook and ordered two pants and a polo T-shirt.*" Two days later, Daraz's office informed me that the goods were being sent to me. When the delivery boy comes to give me the products, I want to open it up and see. Then the delivery boy said, 'You can't take it off now. You'll open it later. You can return even if there is a problem. Then I opened the packet and saw that the pants were low-quality. These pants are worse than the pants they sell in roadside. And the polo T-shirt has a problem with the collar. All three products seem to me to be the reject goods. He added, "*The special concession that Daraz gives is actually a fraud. They give special discounts by increasing the price of goods. I think Daraz should ensure the quality of the product before delivering.*"
- Mohammad Ishan Mirza, a victim of Jatrabari area told '*I bought a power bank from Daraz, I got an old battery in it.*' Daraz cheated on me. My order number was 608738494939962.

- *Sirajul Islam Hriday* ordered a red-black smart wall watch from the electronics component section of the Daraz online page on November 29 last year, 2020. The watch costs Tk 299 but is added to the shipping charge of Tk 60 more. The order number is 60447504103841. Started Code-BDDExADR. After 20 days with an additional bill to SA Paribahan, Daraz opened the packet sits online and hands on his head. What a case! He ordered the clock and came the poor-quality something else. Soon after the customer contacted the messenger of Daraz's Facebook page, he said in a return message that it was no longer possible to return your product. Please check product pictures, colors, details and return policies, including prices, before purchasing the product. Thank you for being with Daraz. The victim said I ordered by looking at the picture. I opened the box and found three thorns instead of the clock. Since then, the online number has not been contacted by call.
- Md. Saheedur Rahman. He ordered the purchase of two fast chargers from Daraz. Daraz charged him Tk 1800 as the price of the two chargers. But he was given two substandard chargers in place of the original charger. *"I was charged eighteen hundred Tk, but I got the charger, it's low quality"* he says. They could be purchased for a maximum of Tk 300.
- Another customer Masoom Billah was cheated by buying a dinner set from Daraz. His order number is 609243310004670. He wrote on Facebook, "I was very happy to get a 1000 Tk refund offer". Mother has been talking about a dinner set for a long time, Let's buy her a dinner set. Getting a delivery offer at Tk 6, I would like to show my mother many models of Daraz and like a dinner set. Since the house is at the Barisal Upazila level, we received from Barisal with the younger brother thinking whether the courier may break down to bring it to upazila. My mother was upset when she opened the packet after being brought home today. My pain is even more. Because I wanted to make online shopping believable to the family members, Daraz broke it all.' He added that the dinner set model did not give the full sets, old model, design change, along with 31 pieces in place of 32 pieces, i.e. curry balls. The family bowed its head, mother directly said, don't buy anything else online. This dinner set so heavy I have to go back to return at a cost of more than Tk 150. Who will take responsibility for the damage caused to the goods while packing again! It would not have been so bad if you had a small thing, but buying my mother would be like this - I can't accept it.'
- Amjad Hossain Liton of Bhakura village of Pirganj upazila of Thakurgaon has been cheated by buying mobile phone sets from Daraz earlier. He took a mobile phone sent from Daraz to the Sundarbans Courier Service in the district city and opened the packet and found three cloth wheel soaps in the phone box. He was angry and shocked by daraz's incident.
- Another victim was Pius Sarkar of Laxmipur. He orders a watch online. He paid Tk 1,800 for this. But he opened the packet and saw two onions instead of watches

Evaly

Evaly is a leading online shopping platform that offers sellers and buyers to directly connect with another. Evaly helps sellers through its platforms where buyers can be contacted with these sellers. Manufacturing is not a motive of Evaly. Evaly has been founded on December 2018; 2 years ago, in Dhaka, the capital of Bangladesh. It is doing business through a online site named 'evaly.com.bd'. It provides different services such as online shopping, Ekhata, Elogistics, Efood, and Ebazar. Evaly has been accused of cheating customers in the name of revenue evasion through technology by capitalizing on e-commerce platforms, cashback and various offers. The policy is not followed in the conduct of e-commerce business in the company. Evaly introduced Bangladesh bank's unlicensed e-wallet system. An intelligence agency investigation has confirmed allegations against Evaly, including money-monitoring, transparency, accountability and lack of accountability in business management. In this situation, the Evaly is falling into its own trap of digital fraud.

Criticism of Evaly

Evaly is one of the most popular e-commerce sites in Bangladesh. Thousands of customers buy products from Evaly nowadays. There are numerous scandals of this company since it's establishment. Some of those are mentioned in the following sections.

- Everything in the Evaly's business system is being operated through digital traps. The big challenge of e-commerce is to get the right products on time. But Evaly is not able to do the job in many cases. With the money withheld, the company informed the customer that the order was cancelled as there was no supply of goods (stock out). Even with the name 'gift card', Evaly is taking advance money from the customer. Those buying gift cards are forced to leave their money behind.
- When the buyer cancels the order after not getting the product in Evaly, his money is deposited in the e-wallet. Evaly himself cancelled the order as there was no supply of goods. Even then the customer's money is deposited in the e-wallet. The customer no longer gets the money back, but has to buy other products and make a good use. Thus, there have been allegations of tactfully money-grabbing of customers' crores of coats under the guise of offers and gift cards. An investigation by a state intelligence agency found such information.
- The search for the Evaly's business trap shows that the customer is tactfully grabbing crores of takas in the name of the offer. Evaly has been adopting a new marketing strategy in the e-commerce market. For example; recently the company had offered to sell iPhones for Tk 30 on laptops at Tk 15. On this offer, the business trap was verified and it was found that he bought a lottery for Tk. 15, 50 laptops got the lucky winner. But 2 lakh people have participated. $2 \text{ lakh} * 15 \text{ tk} = \text{Tk } 30 \text{ lakh}$ their income went up. $50 \text{ laptops at Tk. } 50 \text{ per thousand} = \text{Tk. } 25 \text{ lakhs}$. But they did not buy the product for tk 50,000.

Bought for 35,000. In this case, 50 products have Tk. 15 lakhs for Evaly. Their trap game doesn't end there. They will refund 15 tk to the remaining 195,550 customers. But the condition is that if they buy any other product from here, they will adjust to that money. Evaly played a bit of a Destiny 2000k Limited (MLM) game here. Buying a product worth Tk 200 will have a profit of Tk 20-50. So, in the name of a refund of Tk 15, he left another Tk 5 more than you. And the person who did not buy the product, 15 rupees remained with the company. If 50,000 of this population buy another product to withdraw money, 50,000 products have been sales instead of one of their marketing and 50 laptops.

- Evaly has up to 150 per cent 'browser offer'. There is also an alternative program called 'Campaign'. Goods are supplied in 7 to 45 days through campaigns. Evaly says the authorities have full rights to make any changes, enhancements or changes to the campaign for inevitable reasons. But some customers complain that they are not getting the product at the time of tying up. And the answer to Evaly is that goods are offered subject to stock, even customers can take back the money if they want.
- Evaly product deprived customer Hasan Bulbul said he ordered to buy an Asus laptop. He also deposited the money. After one to two months Evaly informed him that the product was not in supply. There are other brands of laptops with higher rates of supply. That's what the customer is forced to take.
- In response to Evely's cyclone offer, buyer Rafiq Mia recently ordered a product worth Tk 2,650. Instead of that money, he was deducted Tk 26,500 10 times in a row. He issued a report on this. He also complained to customer care. Mailed too. Authorities said the solution will be done within 72 hours. But he did not get a refund even in about a month. It is said that the money was deducted due to a system error in Evaly, but there was no solution. Many like Rafiq Mia and Hasan Bulbul are in uncertainty by falling into the trap of the Evaly. Traders have urged for legislation to stop the fraud in the name of e-commerce in online product purchases. They say accountability has to be ensured. Because of lack of law and lack of accountability, 3.7 million customers of Evaly are now suffering from uncertainty. However, various government agencies are already looking into the activities of Evaly.
- The proceedings in Evaly started for just two years. The company has already sold goods worth Tk 1,500 crore in various techniques. However, the paid-up capital of the company is only Tk 1 crore. The two-year-old company is being accused of various government organizations. Officials investigating the company's business style found many money-calling information in it. Section 45 of the Protection of Consumer Rights Act states that if the goods or services are not properly sold or supplied in return for the price paid, there may be a rigorous or non-labour imprisonment of one year or a fine of not more than Tk 50,000 or both. We are coming to the notice of Evaly, said Bablu Kumar Saha, director general of the Consumer Rights Protection Department. I'm taking the retinue too.

- The paid-up capital of the Evaly company, which started with a paid-up capital of only Tk. 50,000, is still Rs. 50,000. On May 14, 2018, Evaly.com.bd Limited registered from the Office of the Registrar of Joint Capital Companies and Firms (RJSC). Its approved capital is Rs 5 lakh. The company's managing director Mohammad Russell owns 1,000 shares worth Tk. 10. And 4,000 shares are owned by his wife and company chairman Shamima Nasreen. Mohammad Russell and Shamima Nasreen have given Tk 40,000 out of the paid-up capital. In this regard, Mir Zainul Avedin Shivali, Director (Detective), Anti-Corruption Commission (Dudak), said that several allegations against Evaly have been filed by various state agencies. The commission has already approved the investigation of all activities in Evaly, including cheating and money-monitoring. A search team has been formed. Dudak will take legal action against Evaly based on the team's investigation.
- E-commerce firm Evaly has been accused of tactfully hostageing the customer. Deliveries are supposed to be made in 15 days after online shopping but months of waiting are not matched by desired products. At the same time, many customers are suffering from advance money. Recently, a customer ordered a motorcycle for his elder brother from Evaly. He highlighted how he was left out of his house while buying motorcycles on social media. Farooq Islam, a customer, said, "I'm out of the house today by ordering a bike for my elder brother in Evaly." I can't enter the house until I get delivery. Brother, everyone pray for me. He has sought cooperation on how hero bike deliveries are available.
- There have been allegations that the company also not pays back direct money to those whose products are not delivered. The Evaly website is said to be adjusting the money in the customer's account and buying the product later. Which is an offence in the Protection of Consumer Rights Act. Section 45 of the Act states that if the goods or services are not properly sold or supplied in return for the price paid, the under one year can be rigorous or rigorous imprisonment or a fine of not more than Tk 50,000 or both. The victims of the fraud said we will see our money but we can't take it. That means the organization is capitalising on our simplicity and hostageing us. If they can't give us goods, why don't they return the money immediately? They are keeping crores of rupees of customers with them in this way in a month. And with that money Evaly Is Doing Business. They go to another offer without offering one offer product. It is also taking money on that offer. It's like another Destiny2000. Who have grabbed crores of rupees in the name of MLM business.
- Shamim Rafi, a customer, told that after seeing the lucrative advertisements of Evaly, at 50 per cent discount, I ordered three Motorola E5 Plus mobiles and made payments for three mobiles through Development of Tk. 23,70. The mobiles are supposed to be delivered within 15 days but they rotate me because they are not in the stock. They later said I could take the mobile phone Redmi Note 7S. But I must to deposit another 3,000 tk. Since I needed all three mobiles, I paid Evaly by developing another 9,000 Tk and they delivered me mobile phones through a courier service on November 22,

2020. But seeing the delivered mobile and its money receipt, the sky broke on my head. Because the phone they delivered me had only one phone. I aive order three mobile deliveries. When I called the customer care of the Evaly immediately, it was informed that the remaining two mobiles are out of stock that would be refunded. Later, after I made a written complaint on consumer rights, some Officials of Evaly apologized and hung up the remaining phones in the consumer rights director's room. He added that he went to the National Consumer Rights Protection Office and found that many victims had already brought complaints against Evaly. Such victims are coming every day. At the same time, some officials of Evaly are always there to manage these things.

- One victim, who was conditioned not to be named because of the order in Evaly, said the big problem with Evaly is that they don't keep delivery time right. There are also questions about the quality of the product. I'm going to order for about three months and haven't got the product in hand yet. There is no cooperation from the authorities either.
- Haleem, a customer, wrote in comments on the Evaly page, "I haven't yet received a laptop ordered in presale on December 16, 2020. Customer care informed that I would get the product in hand within 15 working days. I didn't give me another call with confidence. So far the entire system is in processing condition. Please give a reasonable reason from the Evaly authorities. An official of the National Consumer Rights Protection Department, who was on condition of anonymity, said assistant directors are taking action on all the complaints that have been received by us. Action is taken as soon as the complaint is proved. On the number of complaints that have been lodged, he said complaints are being lodged against Evaly every day.

Discussion

Thousands of buyers are constantly being duped by buying goods from Daraz, Evaly, and so other online shopping platform. Sources in the consumer department said more than 950 complaints have been reported in the company so far. Some of these complaints have been disposed of through hearings, but most of the complaints are still pending. The Daraz authorities about the allegations, the company's lawyer Ziaur Rahman said that the buyer should not only take responsibility for buying goods from Daraz and cheating a buyer. Because there is an opportunity to verify a product before buying it. Daraz also delivers the goods of various organizations to the buyer through their platforms. If an organization supplies any adulterated goods or substandard goods, it is the responsibility of the organization. According to him, even Daraz take initiatives against those selelrs for example, the buyer who cheated by buying the mobil should also have checked the product. Yet the mobil supplier has blacklisted TS Motors and stopped taking the bill from the company.

It is not just the consumer department that is coming up with complaints against Daraz and Evaly. Social media, Facebook, YouTube, too, have been reported by many who have been duped by buying products from the e-commerce sites. Hundreds of such complaints are doing the rounds on Facebook-YouTube.

In addition, e-cabs, an association of e-commerce entrepreneurs, are also being accused of fraud and cheating every day. Even after so many complaints, there is no remedies. The consumer department where the duped will get remedies does not always match the remedies. Because in many cases the consumer department is giving verdicts in favor of institutions like Daraz and Evaly. According to officials in the department, there is nothing to do if a buyer is duped by buying goods in accordance with the conditions of the e-commerce platform. In this regard, Deputy Director of consumer directorate Manzoor Mohammad Shahriar told that the buyer who was duped by buying a bill could not present the evidence properly. That's why those e-commerce platforms can't be fined.

Recommendations

Here the government is the first party is the most responsible to stop such frauds. The e-commerce platforms have to take responsibility for buying goods from Daraz and cheating a buyer. Because buyers don't see the product supplier, they see Daraz, Evaly, and so others. Consumer law ensures consumer rights. If the consumer department cannot protect the interests of the consumer, it is the consumer department that has to take responsibility. Moreover, since those e-commerce company are in a digital platform, a buyer can also sue under the Digital Act if he cheats. In fact, there is no rule of law in the country. If there was rule of law, institutions like Daraz & Evaly would not have been able to get away with the buyer's constant cheating. Those e-commerce sites have been promoting multi-faceted campaigns on social media and TV screens. Many people are shocked to see the spread of many offers including expensive cars, motorcycles and mobiles for just Tk. 1. In such a situation, is is suggested to set up a task force to close fraud offers. Even a special task force is demanded for a long time. However, there will be a call that everyone should be aware that no one should step into the trap of cheating out of greed.

Conclusion

The cheating news of those e-commerce is not new. Customers are being harassed every day from Evaly. The most common complaint against Daraz is that some seller sends substandard products. Evaly's complaint is that they never deliver goods at the scheduled time. Even waiting for three to four months, the customer is told that the product is not being offered due to stock out. Whatever, there are lots of cheating allegations against these institutions. They have been widely accused of the quality of the product even if they deliver the goods in cash. In the name of giving special discounts, they are offering substandard products to customers. The victims are therefore seen as a 'special fraud' in this particular concession. Hopefully the responsible authority will take the good initiatives. Also, government, more specifically, The Ministry of Commerce also should take initiative to protect consumer rights to see that consumers are not duped. Also they should investigate whether the company is doing business without following government policies.

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